

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B466
 Date: 16 July 2009
 Take Off: 14:07:44Z Basel
 Landing: 18:14:22Z Basel
 Flight Time: 4h 06m 38s

Campaign: CAVIAR
Operating Area: Jungfraujoch

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM	
5	Mission Scientist	Stuart Newman	Met Office	
6	Core Chem / NOx	Stephane Bauguitte	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
8	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
9	SWS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
10	ARIES	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
11	MARSS	Rob King	Met Office	
12	TAFTS	Ralph Beeby	Imperial College	Y
13	TAFTS2	Paul Green	Imperial College	
14	Mission Scientist 2	Chawn Harlow	Met Office	
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flighter log	No log available
ViRC chat log	No log available / ViRC not used
Cloud Physics Processing	No Cloud Physics log produced
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
CVI	No log as no operator on CAVIAR
MARSS	No log available so far
TAFTS	TAFTS operator does not create a log

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	27 Oct 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_144632_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_155800_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_165937_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_165725_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_165924_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_175924_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_144625_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_154625_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_155725_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_144629_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_155756_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090716_r0_b466_165931_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B466
 Date: 16th July 2009
 Project: Caviar
 Location: Jungfrauoch

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
134916		Start-Up	0.70 kft	194	
135230		power change	0.70 kft	195	
135953		taxy	0.70 kft	064	
140744		T/O	0.68 kft	154	
140744	143226	Profile 1	2.0 - 28.1 kft	154	
141224		jw nevz zero	9.4 kft	139	
143226	144335	Run 1	28.1 - 28.0 kft	021	
143715		Sonde 1	28.1 kft	161	
144336	144837	Profile 2	28.0 - 23.0 kft	153	
144639		video	24.7 kft	230	on
144843	150018	Run 2	23.0 - 23.1 kft	305	
145059		Sonde 2	23.1 kft	317	
145205		ovhd jungfrau	23.1 kft	315	
145645		sonde 3	23.0 kft	313	
150316	150521	Profile 3	23.0 - 21.0 kft	294	
150631	150803	Orbit 1	21.1 - 21.2 kft	099	
150834	151021	Orbit 2	21.0 - 20.9 kft	152	
151115	151248	Profile 4	21.0 - 20.1 kft	178	
151249	152534	Run 3	20.1 - 20.0 kft	143	
151924		ovhd jfj	20.0 kft	150	
152558	153010	Profile 5	20.0 - 17.1 kft	011	
152811		Profile 5	18.0 kft	243	interrupt
152920		Profile 5	18.0 kft	320	resume
153015	154030	Run 4	17.0 kft	310	
153156		ovhd jfj	17.0 kft	322	
154031	154124	Profile 6	17.0 - 16.0 kft	317	
154212	154337	Orbit 3	16.0 - 16.1 kft	180	
154432	154528	Orbit 4	16.0 - 16.1 kft	019	
154642	155644	Run 5	16.0 - 16.2 kft	173	
155437		ovhd jfj	16.1 kft	143	
155645	155901	Profile 7	16.3 - 18.0 kft	139	
155902	161134	Run 6	18.0 kft	237	
160259		ovhd jfj	18.0 kft	321	
161134	161658	Profile 8	18.0 - 21.0 kft	299	
161246		Profile 8	19.0 kft	278	interrupt
161350		Profile 8	19.0 kft	032	resume
161509		Profile 8	20.0 kft	151	interrupt
161549		Profile 8	20.0 kft	159	resume
161659	162634	Run 7	21.0 - 21.5 kft	147	
162634	163040	Profile 9	21.5 - 25.0 kft	125	
163040	163934	Run 8	25.0 kft	316	
163115		sonde 4	25.0 kft	318	
163427		sonde 5	25.0 kft	314	
163934	164522	Profile 10	25.0 - 30.0 kft	312	
164522	165208	Run 9	30.0 kft	143	
165033		ovhd jfj	30.0 kft	148	
165546	170615	Run 10	30.1 kft	304	
165900		Sonde 6	30.0 kft	326	
170616	172156	Profile 11	30.1 - 35.0 kft	141	
171442		ovhd jfj	33.8 kft	153	
172030		sonde 7	34.5 kft	330	
172156	172925	Run 11	35.0 kft	309	
172257		sonde 8	35.1 kft	316	
172926	174648	Profile 12	35.0 - 16.0 kft	308	
174133		ovhd jfj	21.6 kft	147	
174648	175659	Run 12	16.0 kft	325	
174834		ovhd jfj	16.0 kft	319	
181422		Land	0.74 kft	153	Basel
181946		Power Lost on taxy.			

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B466 11:48:14-18:16:25

GLon_PARA0611, GLat_PARA0610

LFSB -> LSZB - Overview

NavData Cycle 2009-7 Expires: Thursday, 30 July 2009.

Scale: 1:581170 (1 inch = 7.97 naut mi). Printed on 15 Jul 2009

5 4 7 7 4 9 4 6

FliteStar 9.4.6.0

Sortie brief for FAAM

CAVIAR detachment 2009

Flight no:	B466
Proposed date:	Thursday 16 July 2009
Prepared by:	Stuart Newman
Version no.:	1.0, prepared 15 July 2009 1050L (0850Z)

Aim:	To sample intensively the water vapour structure of the atmosphere above the Jungfrauoch, and measure the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum.
Airfield:	Basel
Flight location:	Swiss Alps in vicinity of Jungfrauoch high altitude research station.
Weather conditions required:	Clear sky (or very nearly clear sky, preferably $\frac{1}{8}$ cloud or less) from surface to space.
Dropsondes:	7 required. To be released from high altitudes only (FL240 and above).

Further sortie details

Coordinates: aim to fly straight and level runs between fixed coordinates

BADEP = 47° 1.6' N, 7° 25.5' E

(Jungfrauoch = 46° 32.9' N, 7° 59.1' E)

A = 46° 22.0' N, 8° 10.0' E

The runs are of approx. 10 mins duration, may be slightly longer at the lowest altitudes.

Orientation: Track approx. 142°T and reciprocal over Jungfrauoch and neighbouring glacier.

Radiometers: ARIES and TAFTS to coordinate their upward and downward views during the straight and level runs. SWS to scan a range of angles except during orbits.

Note that the following flight altitudes are examples only, and in practice these will be chosen by the mission scientist.

Sortie profile

No.	Item	Time	Cumulative time
1.	Take off from Basel at 1400Z.		
2.	Profile ascent via airways to arrive at BADEP at FL280.	0:30	0:30
3.	Perform straight and level run (SLR) at FL280, BADEP to A, dropping one sonde	0:10	0:40
4.	Descending turn to FL240, rate of descent 1000 ft/min	0:05	0:45
5.	Perform two orbits with maximum achievable angle of bank	0:10	0:55
6.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL240, dropping two sondes	0:10	1:05
7.	Descending turn to FL200, rate of descent 1000 ft/min	0:05	1:10
8.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL200	0:10	1:20
9.	Descending turn to FL170, rate of descent 500 ft/min	0:05	1:25
10.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL170	0:15	1:40
11.	Descending turn to FL160, rate of descent 500 ft/min	0:05	1:45
12.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL160	0:15	2:00
13.	Perform two orbits with maximum achievable angle of bank	0:10	2:10
14.	Descending turn to FL150, rate of descent 500 ft/min	0:05	2:15
15.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL150	0:15	2:30
16.	Climbing turn to FL180, rate of climb 500 ft/min	0:05	2:35
17.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL180	0:15	2:50
18.	Climbing turn to FL220, rate of climb 1000 ft/min	0:05	2:55
19.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL220	0:10	3:05
20.	Climbing turn to FL260, rate of climb 1000 ft/min	0:05	3:10
21.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL260, dropping one sonde	0:10	3:20
22.	Climbing turn to FL300, rate of climb 1000 ft/min	0:05	3:25
23.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL300, dropping two sondes	0:10	3:35
24.	Climbing turn to FL350 (or maximum achievable), rate of climb 1000 ft/min	0:10	3:45
25.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL350, dropping one sonde	0:10	3:55
26.	If time allows, perform profile descent from FL350 to FL150. Otherwise end of science. Transit back to Basel	0:10	4:05

Aircraft Scientist's Log

S.M. NEWMAN

Flight No **B466**.....

Date ..16/7/2009....

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~1408		TAKE-OFF			
		8700'			Passing through broken Cu on ascent
		11400'			Currently clear above + below, many Cu on horizon in capped layer below our altitude
141530	↑	FL132	231	47°6', 7°36'	Some high tops around, few Cu towers
					10-20 per cc here (100+ lower) PCASP
142455	↑	FL230	231	46°42', 6°48'	Some towers to starboard at our altitude
142653		FL246	Turning		for air traffic
	R1	FL280	021	46°54', 7°12'	PRE-BADEP start of run
143450		"	Turning		
143714		"	160	46°48', 7°36'	Dropsonde #1
					Consistently broken Cu, few towers, Some breaks
144204					Over JFJ (Jungfraujoch)
144335	end R1	FL280 ↓	in turn	46°24', 8°6'	
	(P2)				
144837	R2	FL230	310	46°18', 8°6'	
145053					Dropsonde #2
					Ahead some v. high towers, clear patches
145645					Dropsonde #3
150316	P3	FL230 ↓		47°12', 7°12'	Clear above + below just here
		FL210			For orbits at 50°
	P ↓	to FL200	165		
151230	R3	FL200	143	46°54', 7°30'	
152040					Some Cu tops around at our level
152150			Turning		

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.466**.....

 Date **16/7/2009**.....

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1526	P (5) ↓	FL200 ↓			Significant hold-up due to air traffic
153009	R4	FL170	311	46°24, 8°	
153545	"	"	316	46°42, 7°42	Relatively clear slot ahead
153759					Clear here
154025	P ↓		317		
154127	(end)				for 2 orbits at 60°
154631	R	FL160	172		Lowest permitted run with clouds ahead, some tops at our level
155414		"			Just missed cloud tops underneath
155633	end.				Start of profile climb to FL180
	R	FL180	318		Clear view of observatory below
160259					Some Cu towers around us above our altitude
	↓				<u>V.</u> close to tower to starboard
161240		FL190			Interrupted profile climb
161345	P ↑				Climb to FL210
161513					Interrupted FL200
161640	R7	FL210	148		Run BADEP → A
162616	end				
1628					Clear view of glacier and JFJ
163040	R8	FL250	317		Dropsonde #4
163428					Dropsonde #5
163642					FWVS seems to be offset from Gen East
163940	end R8				Conditions consistent, with clear gaps and patches/towers of Cu
164612	R9	FL300	143		Looks perfectly clear above
	R10	FL300			A-BADEP for sonde drop
	R10				

Mission scientist debrief for CAVIAR flight B466 on 16 July 2009

S. M. Newman

Debrief

This sortie was planned to investigate the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum over the Jungfraujoch high altitude research station while NPL solar absorption measurements were made from the mountain.

The aircraft passed through broken Cu on ascent from Basel around 8-9,000 ft. It became apparent on approach to the area of operations that many Cu lay within a capped layer below the Jungfraujoch altitude, but there were persistently some cumulus towers with tops significantly higher.

A profile climb through the airways up to the northern point BADEP was followed by a straight and level run (SLR) at Flight Level 280, with the release of two sondes. A run at FL230 was followed by two orbits to characterise any scattering by aerosol from the recent volcanic eruption. Runs at FL200, FL170 and FL160 (the minimum allowed with occasional Cu at this level) were completed over the Jungfraujoch. Two further orbits were performed at low level. A series of runs at ascending levels of FL180, FL210, FL250 and FL300 were carried out to determine the change in radiation with changing temperature and water vapour concentration. It was noticeable that the atmosphere was moist at all levels, never below 60% RH. Dropsondes were released at FL250 and FL300.

A slow climb to FL350 was made for a final high-level run (two more dropsondes); the anti-correlated behaviour of ozone and CO indicated we managed to penetrate the tropopause. A final profile descent was followed by a run at FL160. Throughout the flight it appeared to be clear at high levels, with variable amounts of Cu in the mid- and lower-troposphere.

Summary

A successful first flight of the Swiss CAVIAR campaign. Conditions, although not absolutely ideal, were suitable for clear-air radiative transfer at most levels for much of the sortie.

Instrument issues

Large radiometers appeared to operate well, although TAFTS experienced some problems at times. The CVI hygrometer was inoperable. SID-2 worked sporadically while the other cloud physics kit including PCASP worked well. The FWVS lamp was inadvertently not switched on, so data may be noisy/suspect.

The NPL FTS on the Jungfraujoch had cloud affecting line-of-sight at times.

Cloud Physics Flight Log B466

Date: 16/07/09	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 12:40	DAU1 Time: N/A	DAU2 Time: Set	AUX1 Time: Set	AUX2 Time: Set
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DAU2 Disk space?

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		SID2			
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		Y			
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	2.6	Vref (>7V):	6.2	El #1:	1.2	El#1 V (>1):	-2.1	Comms?:	Y		
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	1	El #32:	2.5	El#32 V (>1):	-1.8				
			Sheath flow	15	El #64:	1.4						
			Spectra ok?	Y	Laser current	78						

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	Y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	Y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	Y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
14:11												CDP CAL CHECK PREFLIGHT 40 AND 15MICRON Heaters on SID2 problems? Noise? CDP noise spikes very regular. Laser voltage of 4.7 too high?
14:32:25	FL280	NOISE		20	0.2	0		0				START RUN 1 (before BADEP)
14:37:18	FL280	0		20	0.28	0		0				SONDE 1
14:47:30	FL240	0		25	0.32	0		0				
14:49:27	FL240	0		25	0.25	0		0				RUN 2
14:51:11	FL240	0		28	0.19	0		0				SONDE2
14:55:32	FL240	0		24	0.2	0		0				TAS set to manual as CIP appears frozen on 10m/s
14:57:02	FL240	0		15	0.24	0		0				SONDE 3
15:02:08	FL230	0		20	0.22	0		0				
15:04:08	FL220	0		25	0.21	0		0				
15:05:23	FL210	0		17	0.32	0		0				
15:10:01	FL210	0		19	0.18	0		0				ORBITS

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
15:19:57	FL200	0		15	0.28	0		0				
15:27:43	FL190	0		90	0.26	0		0				APPROX 15:25 SID2 SPELL WHERE FIFO NOT FULL.
15:28:29	FL180	0		65	0.28	0		0				
15:30:10	FL170	0		15	0.26	0		0				TAS SOURCE SET AS CIP100 AS NOW CLEAR.
15:34:10	FL170	0		20	0.21	0		0				
15:40:04	FL170	0		11	0.24	0		0				
15:47:29	FL160	0		15	0.24	0		0				SID2 LIKES ORBITS!!!
15:56:36	FL160	0		12	0.14	0		0				END RUN
16:00:36	FL180	0		23	0.23	0		0				
16:09:21	FL180	0		12	0.19	0		0				
16:12:35	FL190	0		15	0.17	0		0				PROFILE 3
16:15:10	FL200	0		25	0.25	0		0				
16:16:45	FL210	0		20	0.20	0		0				RUN 7
16:26:16	FL210	0		25	0.22	0		0				END RUN 7
16:28:43	FL230	0		15	0.17	0		0				
16:29:50	FL240	0		25	0.31	0		0				
16:30:42	FL250	0		23	0.27	0		0				START RUN 8
16:45:23	FL300	0		20	0.17	0		0				
16:50:01	FL300	0		30	0.13	0		0				
16:55:13	FL300	0		38	0.22	0		0				
16:58:40	FL300	0		25	0.17	0		0				TAS SOURCE MANUAL = 100m/s
17:07:34	FL310	0		38	0.32	0		0				
17:16:30	FL340	0		30	0.23	0		0				
17:23:00	FL350	0		30	0.23	0		0				FINAL SONDE
17:32:38	FL320	0		87	0.21	0		0				
17:33:12	FL310	0		41	0.28	0		0				
17:34:10	FL300	0		30	0.21	0		0				CHECKED TAS ON CIP. STILL NOT GOOD.
17:35:00	FL290	0		23	0.14	0		0				
17:35:44	FL280	0		23	0.22	0		0				
17:36:33	FL270	0		15	0.28	0		0				
17:37:35	FL260	0		38	0.29	0		0				
17:38:20	FL250	0		23	0.20	0		0				
17:40:16	FL230	0		28	0.20	0		0				
17:42:05	FL210	0		25	0.16	0		0				
17:42:55	FL200	0		16	0.17	0		0				
17:44:00	FL190	0		20	0.17	0		0				

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
17:44:43	FL180	0		27	0.21	0		0				
17:45:53	FL170	0		30	0.23	0		0				
17:46:50	FL160	0		13	0.16	0		0				END RUN START PROFILE. PEAK CONCS AROUND FL165
17:54:05	FL160	0		12	0.14	0		0				
17:57:08	FL160	0		20	0.20	0		0				END RUN
18:02:38	FL130	0		25	0.19	0		0				
18:04:07	FL110	0		30	0.22	0		0				
18:04:45	FL100	0		80	0.17	0		0				
18:05												Heaters off. LWC off

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:	N/A	
	Flow:		
2DC	El#1:	1.4	
	El#32:	1.9	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	6.5	
	Flow:	OK	
CDP	Laser V:	4	
FFSSP	Ref V:		
SID 2	Laser V:		NOISY
Rack Equipment			Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.708MB

Flight:

B466

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B466

Date: 16/7/09

Instruments

1. Neph/psap pc had been given fwvs ip address. Caused major network problems pre-flight!

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

ARIES flight log

Flight: B466

page 1 of 2

Date: 16/7/09 Operator(s): D. TINDENAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: SWITZERLAND CAUIAR

Scans: either "[iGMS]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
1415							Test script CN2 Cauir Nadir Zenith 30s (CH 30s N 30s 230s) repeated
143139	FL250	CN2		0	30	70	Temp Some slightly strange looking spectra etc
144850	FL240	CN2		0	30	71	
150020	"	"		0	30	70	stopped script
151951	FL200	CN2		0	30	70	
152609	"	"		0	30	70	stopped.
152830	FL180	CN2		0	30	30	
152920	"	"					stopped
153018	FL170	CN2		0	70	30	
154030	"	"		0	70	30	stop
154632	FL160	CN2		0	70	30	
155700	"	"		0	71	30	stop
160050	FL180	CN2		0	70	31	
161250	"	"		0	71	31	stop
161646	FL210	CN2		0	71	31	
162530	"	"		0	72	31	stop
163040	FL250	CN2		0	71	30	
163220	"	"		0	71	30	Opened shutter oops
164230	FL280			0	71	30	stopped
164572	FL300	CN2		0	71	31	
165218	"	"		"	"	"	SS Stop
165607	FL300	CN2		0	71	30	
170610	FL300	CN2		0	71	31	stop
172153	FL350	CN2		0	70	31	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	16/07/09	Flight	B466	log pages
Operator(s)	Rob King		Campaign	CAVIAR		
Departure			Arrival			

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	1235
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	1240
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	1240
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	311	Cold	315	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	

B466_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

11:37:42.16 --- - - -
11:37:42.16 --- - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:37:42.16 --- - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:37:42.16 --- - - - +++ Flight no. B466
11:37:42.16 --- - - -
11:37:57.67 --- - - - *** Operator: Stuart Rogers
11:38:30.68 SWS - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:38:35.60 USH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:38:38.84 LSH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:39:01.99 USH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:39:01.99 LSH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:39:02.00 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:39:05.95 --- - - - Reset shutters.
11:39:14.02 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
11:39:17.73 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
11:39:23.25 USH - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
11:39:26.90 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
11:39:34.33 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
11:39:38.45 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
11:39:52.88 --- - - - Reset shutters.
11:40:08.73 SWS - - - Telescope motor initialised.
11:40:14.31 SWS -0.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
11:40:25.64 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
11:40:27.30 SWS 173.6 - - - Telescope stopped.
11:40:30.92 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
11:40:32.59 SWS -2.3 - - - Telescope stopped.
11:50:32.46 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to 87.939
11:50:33.57 SWS 87.9 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:35:55.90 --- - - - Reset shutters.
12:36:00.83 --- - - - Reset shutters.
12:36:05.95 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
12:36:05.98 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
12:36:06.50 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
12:36:07.40 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:36:07.59 USH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:36:07.94 LSH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:36:19.17 SWS 87.9 - - - Telescope sent to -60.000
12:36:20.85 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:21.56 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:22.27 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:23.00 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:23.70 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:24.41 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:25.13 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:25.84 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:26.55 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:27.27 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:27.98 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:28.69 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:29.16 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:36:46.95 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:47.42 SWS -60.0 - - - Telescope sent to -55.000
12:36:47.99 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:48.70 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:49.41 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:50.12 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:50.84 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:51.55 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:52.27 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:52.98 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:53.70 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:36:54.72 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:37:00.08 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:37:16.75 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to -55.000
12:37:25.14 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:37:44.79 SWS 60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

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12:38:04.45 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:38:24.09 SWS 60.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:38:35.68 SWS -7.5 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:38:54.05 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:38:54.57 SWS -7.5 - - - Telescope sent to -55.000
12:38:55.13 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:38:55.84 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:38:56.57 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:38:57.28 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:38:57.99 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:38:58.71 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:38:59.42 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:39:00.43 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:39:13.17 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope sent to -55.000
12:39:13.73 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:39:14.46 SWS -7.5 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:39:15.17 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:39:15.88 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:39:16.34 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:39:20.00 SWS -7.4 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:39:23.89 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:39:24.42 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to -55.000
12:39:24.99 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:39:25.71 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:39:26.72 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:39:39.37 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to -55.000
12:39:47.76 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
12:39:57.32 SWS 0.3 - - - Telescope stopped.
12:40:10.97 SWS - - - Idling
12:40:13.05 USH - - - Idling
12:40:14.63 LSH - - - Idling
12:40:18.82 LSH - - - Instrument closed.
12:40:20.03 USH - - - Instrument closed.
12:40:21.56 SWS - - - Instrument closed.
12:40:24.92 SWS - - - Telescope disabled.
12:40:26.71 --- - - - *** SHUTTING DOWN...
12:40:27.05 SWS - - - Telescope motor control quit.
12:58:30.53 --- - - -
12:58:30.53 --- - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
12:58:30.54 --- - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
12:58:30.58 --- - - - +++ Flight no. B466
12:58:30.58 --- - - -
12:58:41.46 SWS - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:58:52.44 USH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:58:53.73 LSH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:59:07.32 USH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:59:07.32 LSH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:59:07.33 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:00:34.99 --- - - - Reset shutters.
13:00:41.13 SWS - - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
13:00:53.40 SWS - - - 100 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:01:33.60 USH - - - 20 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 20ms.
13:01:36.75 USH - - - 100 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:01:40.97 LSH - - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
13:01:44.21 LSH - - - 100 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:01:49.13 LSH - - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
13:01:51.68 --- - - - Reset shutters.
13:02:09.76 SWS - - - ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
13:29:14.09 SWS - - - Telescope disabled.
13:29:31.55 SWS - - - ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
13:29:36.88 SWS - - - Idling
13:29:37.15 SWS - - - Telescope disabled.
13:29:39.65 USH - - - Idling
13:29:41.16 LSH - - - Idling
13:29:49.13 LSH - - - Instrument closed.
13:29:51.87 USH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:29:52.02 SWS - - - Instrument closed.
13:29:54.56 USH - - - Idling

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13:29:59.06 USH - - - - Instrument closed.
13:30:01.41 --- - - - - *** SHUTTING DOWN...
13:30:01.85 SWS - - - - Telescope motor control quit.
13:30:23.44 --- - - - -
13:30:23.44 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:30:23.44 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
13:30:23.44 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B466
13:30:23.44 --- - - - -
13:30:34.33 SWS - - - - ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
13:30:45.24 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
13:30:47.23 --- - - - - *** SHUTTING DOWN...
13:30:47.85 SWS - - - - Telescope motor control quit.
13:31:39.54 --- - - - -
13:31:39.54 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:31:39.54 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
13:31:39.54 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B466
13:31:39.54 --- - - - -
13:31:53.13 SWS - - - - ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
13:31:59.93 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
13:31:59.99 --- - - - - *** SHUTTING DOWN...
13:32:01.24 SWS - - - - Telescope motor control quit.
13:35:28.68 --- - - - -
13:35:28.68 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:35:28.68 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
13:35:28.68 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B466
13:35:28.68 --- - - - -
13:35:34.49 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
13:35:42.28 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
13:35:43.99 SWS 173.9 - - - - Telescope stopped.
13:35:46.60 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
13:35:48.34 SWS -5.9 - - - - Telescope stopped.
13:35:59.12 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:36:00.90 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:36:02.15 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:36:11.51 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:36:11.52 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:36:11.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:36:13.88 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:36:18.83 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
13:36:21.78 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:36:27.43 USH - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
13:36:30.52 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:36:35.24 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:36:38.16 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:36:46.54 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:36:47.03 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:36:47.05 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:36:47.97 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:36:48.46 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:36:48.66 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:50:51.92 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
13:50:54.79 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
13:50:58.53 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:08:21.13 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:08:26.83 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:08:26.86 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:08:26.94 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:08:28.27 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:08:28.59 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:08:28.67 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:08:33.77 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:08:33.97 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:08:34.07 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:10:03.60 --- - - - - *** T/O 1408-ish
14:23:49.56 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
14:23:52.73 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

14:23:54.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:45.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:45.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:45.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:46.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:46.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:47.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:32:48.41	---	-	-	-	-	***
14:38:45.10	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:38:45.56	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -60.000
14:38:53.72	SWS	-5.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:39:03.49	SWS	-5.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:39:04.62	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:39:10.56	SWS	-5.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:39:27.68	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:39:34.17	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:43:39.20	SWS	-5.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:43:59.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** Telescope problems...
14:44:16.10	SWS	-5.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:44:23.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
14:44:30.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
14:44:39.28	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:44:48.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
14:45:13.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
14:45:32.86	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 164.510
14:45:34.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:45:34.56	SWS	164.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:45:41.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:45:56.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:46:04.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:46:06.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:46:19.98	SWS	164.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:46:21.66	SWS	-0.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:46:26.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
14:46:44.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
14:46:57.74	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
14:47:04.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:04.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:04.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:05.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:47:05.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:47:06.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:47:07.30	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:47:07.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:08.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:08.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:27.02	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:47:46.82	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:48:06.43	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:48:26.12	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:48:45.83	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:49:05.67	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:49:25.44	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:49:45.20	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:50:04.94	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:50:24.77	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:50:44.45	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:51:04.17	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:51:24.07	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:51:27.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:27.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:27.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:28.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:51:29.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:51:29.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:51:43.83	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:52:03.59	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:52:23.38	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:52:43.16	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

14:53:02.96	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:53:22.67	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:53:42.50	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:54:02.36	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:54:21.94	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:54:41.48	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:55:01.28	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:55:21.14	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:55:40.80	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:56:00.69	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:56:20.45	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:56:39.80	SWS	59.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:56:59.50	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:57:18.83	SWS	59.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:57:38.73	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
14:57:58.08	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
14:58:08.88	SWS	-2.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:58:20.96	SWS	-2.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:58:28.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:28.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:28.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:29.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:30.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:30.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:30.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:59:33.92	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:03:50.66	---	-	-	-	-	***
15:05:16.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:17.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:17.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:18.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:18.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:18.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:28.12	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 10ms.
15:05:30.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:31.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:15.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** Orbit 50deg(?) left
15:07:56.16	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 15ms.
15:07:57.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:59.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:19.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** Orbit 50deg right
15:08:36.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:10:13.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:10:23.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:24.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:31.09	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 30ms.
15:10:37.28	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
15:10:48.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:50.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:58.95	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:11:59.37	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
15:12:10.63	SWS	57.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:11.31	SWS	53.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:12.04	SWS	49.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:12.77	SWS	44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:13.49	SWS	40.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:14.52	SWS	34.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:12:20.59	SWS	34.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:12:27.86	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:28.27	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
15:12:39.45	SWS	58.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:40.14	SWS	54.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:40.86	SWS	49.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:41.60	SWS	45.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:42.33	SWS	40.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:43.06	SWS	36.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:43.84	SWS	31.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:44.59	SWS	27.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:45.31	SWS	22.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

15:12:46.05	SWS	18.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:46.80	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:47.54	SWS	9.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:48.25	SWS	5.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:12:48.97	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:49.70	SWS	-3.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:50.42	SWS	-7.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:51.14	SWS	-12.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:51.86	SWS	-16.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:52.58	SWS	-20.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:53.30	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:54.05	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:54.81	SWS	-34.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:55.54	SWS	-38.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:56.27	SWS	-42.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:57.00	SWS	-47.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:57.70	SWS	-51.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:12:58.42	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:13:18.32	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:13:37.71	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:13:57.07	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:14:16.97	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:14:36.83	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:14:45.60	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
15:14:48.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:48.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:48.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:49.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:49.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:49.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:56.32	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:15:15.73	SWS	59.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:15:35.21	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:15:54.63	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:16:14.53	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:16:33.89	SWS	59.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:16:53.78	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:17:13.69	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:17:33.52	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:17:53.39	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:18:13.29	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:18:32.66	SWS	59.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:18:52.43	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:19:11.84	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:19:31.19	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:19:51.08	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:20:10.98	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:20:30.35	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:20:50.24	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:21:10.14	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:21:30.00	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:21:49.39	SWS	59.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:22:09.17	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:22:24.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:22:28.99	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:22:29.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:22:48.41	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:23:07.86	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:23:27.34	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:23:46.73	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:24:05.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:24:06.52	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:24:26.43	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:24:45.87	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:25:05.42	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:25:25.19	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:25:45.08	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:26:04.97	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:26:24.34	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

15:26:25.09	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:26:25.82	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:26:26.55	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:26:27.27	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:26:28.01	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:26:28.73	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:26:29.45	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:26:30.17	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:26:30.73	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:26:44.11	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:26:45.26	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:26:49.07	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
15:26:57.61	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:27:16.98	SWS	59.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:27:27.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:27:29.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:27:33.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:27:36.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:27:36.40	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:27:45.89	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:27:48.71	SWS	-0.1	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:28:08.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS VIS+NIR have dropped out
15:28:32.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:28:38.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:28:48.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
15:28:52.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:29:05.71	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:29:09.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:29:34.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS+NIR restarted
15:30:07.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:07.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:07.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:08.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:08.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:30:09.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:30:09.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:19.50	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
15:30:28.05	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:30:31.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL170
15:30:47.38	SWS	59.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:31:07.28	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:31:26.64	SWS	59.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:31:45.98	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:32:05.87	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:32:25.35	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:32:44.71	SWS	59.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:33:04.10	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:33:23.53	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:33:42.98	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:34:02.31	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:34:21.77	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:34:41.16	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:35:00.65	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:35:20.13	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:35:39.49	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:35:58.84	SWS	59.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:36:18.29	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:36:37.71	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:36:57.09	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:37:16.45	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:37:35.89	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:37:48.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:55.30	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:38:14.87	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:38:34.25	SWS	59.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:38:53.75	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:39:02.80	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:39:06.64	SWS	-3.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:39:17.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:39:19.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:43.17	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 10ms.
15:41:44.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:46.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:59.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** Orbit 60 deg left
15:42:47.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:44:07.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** Orbit 60deg left
15:44:34.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:45:37.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:45:38.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:11.00	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
15:46:15.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:16.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:44.54	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:46:44.98	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
15:46:55.76	SWS	59.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:46:56.46	SWS	56.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:46:57.16	SWS	52.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:46:57.89	SWS	47.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:46:58.64	SWS	43.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:46:59.38	SWS	38.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:47:00.10	SWS	34.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:47:00.86	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:47:01.56	SWS	25.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:47:02.29	SWS	21.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:47:03.02	SWS	17.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:47:03.74	SWS	12.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:47:04.47	SWS	8.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:47:05.21	SWS	3.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:47:05.94	SWS	-0.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:06.66	SWS	-4.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:07.39	SWS	-9.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:08.11	SWS	-13.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:08.87	SWS	-18.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:09.60	SWS	-22.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:10.34	SWS	-27.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:11.07	SWS	-31.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:11.79	SWS	-35.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:12.49	SWS	-39.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:13.22	SWS	-44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:13.95	SWS	-48.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:14.66	SWS	-52.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:15.40	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:47:34.90	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:47:54.25	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:48:13.80	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:48:33.33	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:48:39.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:39.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:39.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:40.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:41.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:41.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:41.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:48:48.92	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:48:52.87	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:48:53.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:53.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:53.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:55.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:48:55.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:55.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:02.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:12.36	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:49:31.93	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:49:51.36	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:50:10.75	SWS	59.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:50:30.19	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:50:49.68	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

15:51:09.61	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:51:29.19	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:51:48.70	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:52:08.24	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:52:27.76	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:52:47.23	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:53:06.75	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:53:26.21	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:53:45.88	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:54:05.78	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:54:25.25	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:54:44.67	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:55:04.13	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:55:23.68	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:55:43.23	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:56:02.82	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:56:22.37	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:56:41.90	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:57:01.49	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:57:16.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:57:21.06	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:57:40.58	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:57:51.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:51.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:51.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:53.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:53.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:53.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:55.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:58:00.00	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:58:19.60	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:58:39.23	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:58:58.70	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:59:18.33	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
15:59:37.88	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
15:59:57.33	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:00:17.04	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:00:36.67	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:00:56.30	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:01:15.94	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:01:19.24	SWS	42.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:01:24.69	SWS	42.3	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
16:01:26.44	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:02:46.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:03:08.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:03:23.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** Over cloud?
16:03:29.87	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:03:30.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:03:31.55	SWS	-5.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:03:39.35	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
16:03:47.99	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:04:07.58	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:04:27.20	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:04:46.75	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:05:06.46	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:05:26.08	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:05:45.76	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:06:05.39	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:06:25.02	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:06:44.52	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:07:04.08	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:07:23.73	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:07:43.31	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:08:02.84	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:08:22.42	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:08:42.06	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:09:01.68	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:09:21.40	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:09:41.09	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0

16:10:00.78	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:10:20.41	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:10:40.03	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:10:59.63	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:11:19.22	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:11:38.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:11:38.85	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:11:39.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:39.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:39.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:40.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:11:40.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:11:40.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:11:58.47	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:12:18.32	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:12:38.04	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:12:57.61	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:13:17.29	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:13:37.11	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:13:56.78	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:14:16.52	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:14:32.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:14:36.28	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:14:56.01	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:15:15.72	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:15:35.41	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:15:55.09	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:16:14.83	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:16:34.58	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:16:54.24	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:17:13.91	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:17:33.50	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:17:53.15	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:18:12.92	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:18:32.47	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:18:52.27	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:19:12.04	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:19:31.85	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:19:51.60	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:20:11.48	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:20:31.14	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:20:50.85	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:21:10.60	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:21:30.36	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:21:50.30	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:22:09.71	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:22:29.19	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:22:49.00	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:23:08.61	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:23:28.50	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:23:48.35	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:24:08.10	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:24:27.93	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:24:47.60	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:25:07.17	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:25:26.86	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:25:46.58	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:26:06.24	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:26:22.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:26:25.97	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:26:45.77	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:27:05.49	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:27:25.28	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:27:45.02	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:28:04.81	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:28:24.56	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:28:44.28	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:28:45.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:45.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:28:45.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:47.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:28:47.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:28:47.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:29:04.11	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:29:23.92	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:29:43.61	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:30:03.47	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:30:23.36	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:30:43.21	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:31:02.98	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:31:22.90	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:31:42.65	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:32:02.52	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:32:22.36	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:32:41.74	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:33:01.49	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:33:21.35	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:33:41.14	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:34:00.94	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:34:20.85	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:34:40.62	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:35:00.52	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:35:20.24	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:35:40.16	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:35:59.52	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:36:18.94	SWS	59.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:36:38.80	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:36:58.56	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:37:18.42	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:37:38.26	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:37:57.98	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:38:17.85	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:38:37.68	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:38:57.48	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:39:17.27	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:39:36.70	SWS	59.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:39:55.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:55.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:55.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:56.58	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:39:56.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:57.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:57.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:16.45	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:40:36.28	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:40:55.70	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:41:15.66	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:41:32.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:41:35.58	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:41:55.49	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:42:15.33	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:42:34.77	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:42:54.59	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:43:14.53	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:43:34.38	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:43:54.23	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:44:14.13	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:44:34.03	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:44:53.92	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:45:13.78	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:45:33.65	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:45:53.58	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:46:13.44	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:46:33.34	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:46:53.22	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:47:12.80	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:47:32.52	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:47:52.44	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0

16:48:12.24	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:48:32.16	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:48:51.50	SWS	59.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:49:11.25	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:49:31.12	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:49:50.92	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:50:10.76	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:50:30.56	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:50:50.39	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:51:09.77	SWS	-54.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:51:29.15	SWS	59.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:51:48.50	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:52:08.34	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:52:11.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:52:11.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:52:11.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:52:12.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:12.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:13.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:27.77	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:52:46.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:52:47.13	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:53:06.98	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:53:23.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:53:26.88	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:53:46.35	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:54:05.90	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:54:25.42	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:54:44.82	SWS	59.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:55:04.25	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:55:23.70	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:55:43.49	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:56:02.88	SWS	59.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:56:22.29	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:56:32.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:56:32.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:56:32.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:56:34.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:56:34.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:56:34.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:56:42.16	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:57:02.07	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:57:21.50	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:57:41.00	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:58:00.35	SWS	59.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:58:19.88	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:58:39.37	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:58:58.83	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:59:18.69	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
16:59:38.15	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
16:59:57.61	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:00:17.15	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:00:36.59	SWS	59.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:00:56.03	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:01:15.42	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:01:35.32	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:01:54.83	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:02:14.77	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:02:34.24	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:02:54.17	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:03:13.57	SWS	59.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:03:33.44	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:03:52.87	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:04:12.28	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:04:31.73	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:04:51.14	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:05:11.09	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:05:30.48	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:05:49.90	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

17:06:09.35	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:06:29.17	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:06:48.67	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:07:08.50	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:07:27.91	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:07:47.27	SWS	59.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:08:06.67	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:08:17.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:08:17.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:08:17.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:08:18.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:08:18.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:08:19.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:08:19.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:08:20.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:08:26.59	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:08:28.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:08:29.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:08:46.03	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:09:05.94	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:09:25.42	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:09:44.95	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:10:04.55	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:10:24.01	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:10:43.49	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:11:02.91	SWS	59.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:11:22.43	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:11:41.83	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:12:01.76	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:12:21.20	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:12:40.74	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:13:00.19	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:13:19.64	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:13:39.56	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:13:59.09	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:14:18.55	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:14:38.02	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:14:57.89	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:15:17.35	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:15:36.75	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:15:56.61	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:16:12.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:16:14.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:16:16.04	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:16:20.72	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:16:35.86	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:16:45.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS NIR dropped out, VIS OK
17:16:50.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:16:55.27	SWS	59.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:16:56.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
17:17:04.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
17:17:06.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:17:14.87	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:17:19.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS NIR back
17:17:34.30	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:17:53.75	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:18:13.21	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:18:32.80	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:18:52.30	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:19:11.85	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:19:31.25	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:19:50.63	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:20:08.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:09.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
17:20:10.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:10.27	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:20:12.89	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:20:16.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:18.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

17:20:22.71	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
17:20:26.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:27.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:29.71	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:20:49.27	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:21:08.64	SWS	-54.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:21:28.10	SWS	59.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:21:47.61	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:21:50.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:50.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:50.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:52.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:52.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:52.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:07.18	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:22:26.81	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:22:46.32	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:23:05.92	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:23:25.41	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:23:44.97	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:24:04.70	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:24:24.61	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:24:44.21	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:25:03.87	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:25:23.41	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:25:42.96	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:26:02.56	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:26:22.05	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:26:41.60	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:27:01.40	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:27:21.06	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:27:40.74	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:28:00.32	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:28:19.90	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:28:39.39	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:28:58.95	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:29:18.58	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:29:38.18	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:29:57.75	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:30:17.39	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:30:36.86	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:30:56.42	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:31:16.01	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:31:35.54	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:31:50.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:31:50.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:31:50.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:31:51.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:51.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:52.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:31:55.15	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
17:31:55.18	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:31:56.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:31:58.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:14.71	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:32:34.14	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:32:53.82	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:33:13.30	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:33:32.80	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:33:52.53	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:34:12.09	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:34:31.55	SWS	59.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:34:50.95	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:35:10.65	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:35:30.23	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:35:49.99	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:36:09.51	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:36:28.90	SWS	59.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:36:48.43	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0

17:37:08.01	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:37:27.61	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:37:47.16	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:38:06.75	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:38:26.24	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:38:45.90	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:39:05.34	SWS	59.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:39:24.95	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:39:44.65	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:39:57.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:39:57.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:39:58.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:39:59.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:39:59.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:39:59.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:40:04.23	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:40:23.82	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:40:43.66	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:41:03.25	SWS	60.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:41:22.95	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:41:42.48	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:42:02.26	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:42:21.96	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:42:41.69	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:43:01.35	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:43:20.96	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:43:40.63	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:44:00.25	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:44:19.89	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:44:39.57	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:44:59.26	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:45:18.98	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:45:38.62	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:45:58.25	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:46:17.87	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:46:37.59	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:46:57.19	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:16.99	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:47:36.65	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:47:56.29	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:48:16.00	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:48:35.83	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:48:55.56	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:49:15.32	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:49:35.06	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:49:54.76	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:50:14.63	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:50:34.37	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:50:54.23	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:51:13.81	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:51:33.50	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:51:53.18	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:52:12.87	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:52:32.67	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:52:52.45	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:53:12.19	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:53:31.90	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:53:51.65	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:54:11.48	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:54:31.21	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:54:51.08	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:55:10.78	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:55:30.57	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:55:50.29	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:56:10.04	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:56:29.78	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:56:49.55	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:57:06.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:06.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

17:57:07.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:08.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:08.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:08.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:09.39	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:57:29.12	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
17:57:48.89	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 60.0
17:57:58.99	SWS	3.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
17:58:03.45	SWS	3.3	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
17:58:37.03	SWS	-	250	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
17:58:39.78	USH	-	250	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
17:58:43.04	LSH	-	250	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
18:04:41.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:04:41.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:04:41.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:04:42.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:04:42.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:04:43.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:16:02.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:16:03.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:16:05.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:16:06.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:16:08.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:16:09.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:16:10.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:16:12.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:16:14.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:16:38.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
18:16:42.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
18:16:47.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
18:16:54.46	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
18:17:38.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
18:17:47.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** SHUTTING DOWN...
18:17:47.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor control quit.